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GOODWILL OF LIBRARY USERS AND ITS IMPACT ON SERVICES: A STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The paper succinctly describes the concept of goodwill, nature and value, intellectual capital resources, viewpoints of library goodwill, perspectives and User's goodwill and its impacts on functioning of library, services and working staff. It reveals that 64.70 % goodwill generates among the users through maintaining good relations by the library staff, 64% rendering quality services, 92% leadership, promptness, and skillful policy, 84.70 by creating well behaviour with various types of readers, 47.05 % library staff should be punctual in timing with attachment and affinity in public library readers as they comes under the umbrella of grass root users. The goodwill generates 80.83 % intangible asset which invisible and 92.50 % develop publicity of library automatically. It was concluded that goodwill totally depends on the behaviour and prompt services to the users to save their times.

Keywords:

Goodwill, Library/KRC, Users, intangible assets.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In changing scenario there is major role of intellectual capital in global economy and in this new economic environment, data, information and knowledge are considered to be essential factors for decision making. The various types of intellectual capital is provided by the Libraries/ Knowledge Resource Centers and the main aim and object of these centers are to collect, process and disseminate the conventional and nonconventional much needed information to the users as per their needs and requirement. The professionals in library science have to follow new workflows, roles, modernize information uses, need of users, social relation and contacts considering the future few year's developments to cater to the informational needs of the users as in recent years this transition process is not easy and is rarely smooth. The concept of Library without wall, Virtual, Paperless, Digital, Video, Online and Lending Library is coming to you and Web Library has taken the place of conventional libraries.

The users are the soul of libraries and their goodwill plays a major role from both side i.e. library and users to improve the services and use of library. Goodwill is an intangible asset that is listed collaterally in the balance sheet of library and goodwill although intangible assets have no physical form; their presence increases the services and importance of library. Goodwill is loosely divided into personal, intellectual and business goodwill. Together they reflect the value of the time and energy which spent creating and growing the library services. The book value of goodwill is the difference but in some cases, the value of goodwill can exceed that of the physical assets.

It is not easy service to acquire the goodwill of the users for librarian. It depends on the availability of adequate infrastructure, conventional and non-conventional collection development, well trained and qualified human resources modernize services, and facilities, skill, leadership, working skill, occasion awareness and behaviour of librarian and staff with users, status of rendering information services, collaboration with other institutes and interest. Considering the major role and significance of goodwill of library users and its impact on the use of services the study of academic, research, special and public library users was carried out by collecting and analyzing data to fulfill the aims and object of the study .

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the concept of library goodwill
- To observe the users of various types of libraries/KRC
- To verify the users goodwill about Library/KRC
- To find out the various types of approaches of library goodwill
- To search an impact of goodwill on library/KRC

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study was limited within the jurisdiction of only two districts i.e. Gadchiroli and Chandrapur in backward and tribal region of eastern Maharashtra .The study was mainly concerned with the goodwill of users of libraries and its impact on library services and therefore the scope covered users of university, college, institute, high school, primary and public libraries comprising Agricultural, Non Agricultural, and professionals like arts, science, commerce, law, engineering, medical , and pharmaceuticals faculties libraries.

Table 1: Group of Libraries

Group	Nature of Libraries	Category of Libraries	Number of Libraries			
			Urban		Rural	
			Total	Surveyed	Total	Surveyed
A	Academic Libraries	University -Gadchiroli	01	01	000	00
		College –Gadchiroli	15	15	074	24
		Chandrapur	18	18	130	39
B	Research Libraries	Krishi Vidyanan Kendra	01	01	000	00
C	Special Libraries	Agricultural Libraries	02	02	000	00
D	School Libraries	High-school & Primary				

E	District Libraries Public Libraries	District-Gadchiroli and Chandrapur	02	02	000	00
		Public – Chandrapur	15	15	162	48
		Gadchiroli	12	12	125	36
F	NGO Libraries	SEARCH/LBP	00	00	002	02
Total Libraries			66	66	493	149

Source: website SEARC- Shodhgram LBP- Lok Biradari Prakalp

Table 2: Cadre of Library Users

Group	Nature of Libraries	Category of Libraries	Cadre of Library Users
A	Academic Libraries	University -Gadchiroli College –Gadchiroli Chandrapur	Academic staff, Teachers, Scientist, Research scholars, Students, other users
B	Research Libraries	Krishi Vidyayan Kendra	Scientist, Research scholars, Students
C	Special Libraries	Agricultural Libraries	Academic staff, Teachers, Scientist, Research scholars, Students, Industrialists, Farmers, other users
D	School Libraries	High-school & Primary	Students , Teachers
E	District Libraries Public Libraries	District-Gadchiroli and Chandrapur Public – Chandrapur Gadchiroli	All kinds of People, Lawyers, Doctors, Teachers, Student, Businessman. Farmers, Labors, Hawkers, Rickshaw drivers
F	NGO Libraries	SEARCH/LBP	Local persons, concerned users

Source: website SEARC- Shodhgram LBP- Lok Biradari Prakalp

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Choudhary et.al (2011), a practical and rather simple example for explaining the goodwill produced by a library is provided by Choudhary et.al. Let us assume that the library expenses for acquiring printed and electronic resources are R, with S being the total library expenses (E) are $E=R+S$. A desired outcome for the library would be the goodwill, denoted by $G=SO-E$, where SO is the successful outcomes and E the total expenses for achieving them.

Sidoroko and Yang (2011), recently a number of papers have commented on the goodwill created by library operations and services, while others make suggestion for the creation of library goodwill (Walden 2006)

Marilla D.Svinicki and Barbara A. Schwartz (1998) Positive motivators are less powerful, but have desirable side effects of long term goodwill and positive affect towards the resources available in the library.

Cam Merritt (2015)"Goodwill" on a company's balance sheet represents value that the company gained when it acquired another business but that it can't assign to any particular asset of that

business. Goodwill doesn't always affect a company's net income, but if that goodwill becomes "impaired," the effect can be substantial.

5. METHODOLOGY

The richness of library is totally based on the optimum use of library and services and it was found in a pilot survey that the goodwill of library users plays crucial role and considering this the content "Goodwill of Library Users and its Impact on Services" was selected for the study.

The cluster sampling method was used to collect the data and particular groups were organized as the entire population of users was unclear. The randomly sample assigned for study so that various library users participants better represent the larger group from which they're drawn.

The data was collected through personal visits, interview, and observation, discussion and Online questionnaire comprising infrastructures, collection development with e-resources; modernize services, human resources, and facilities users' goodwill towards library, types of approaches of library goodwill and impact of user's goodwill on libraries.

DEFINITION OF "LIBRARY GOODWILL"

At Goodwill, we are committed to respect, integrity, trust and operational excellence. We believe in the power of work.

Marshall Field (American Businessman, 1834- 1906) "*Goodwill is the one and only asset that competition cannot undersell or destroy.*"

Hayn and Hughes (2006) Goodwill is viewed as an asset by the market and the decline in the value of goodwill is used by investors to value the firm as a whole. Therefore, goodwill represents the value and performance of an entire entity.

Rokade S.M.(2015) Library Goodwill is an intangible asset that arises as a result of acquisition of one Library or Knowledge Resource Center by another for a premium value. The value of a Library's quality services, close, good and active relation with users, concrete users base, proper, skillful, supportive and good staff relations and availability of modernize techniques and technology represent goodwill. Goodwill is not a physical asset like buildings or equipment but it is considered an intangible asset. Goodwill is very valuable for the development of library and is the assets of library balance sheet but it is very difficult to calculate the cost or price. It has also a invisible power to moor or mar the institute when it became negative.

6. RESULT AND DICUSSION

6.1. USER'S GOODWILL TOWARDS LIBRARY

Table 3: Users of Libraries and their value in support of goodwill

Group	Nature of Libraries	Classes of Users of Libraries	Nature & Value of goodwill		
			Approache s	Total 340	Value %
A	Academic Libraries	Academic staff, Teachers,	Good	220	64.70

		Scientist, Research scholars, Students, other users	relation	340	
B	Research Libraries	Scientist, Research scholars, Students	Quality services	32 50	64.00
C	Special Libraries	Academic staff, Teachers, Scientist, Research scholars, Students, Industrialists, Farmers, other users	Leadership Promptness Skillful policy	46 50	92.00
D	School Libraries	Students , Teachers	Well behaviour	288 340	84.70
E	District Libraries Public Libraries	All kinds of People, Lawyers, Doctors, Teachers, Student, Businessman. Farmers, Labors, Hawkers, Rickshaw drivers	Punctual in timing Attachment affinity	160 340	47.05
F	NGO Libraries	Local persons, concerned users	Quality collection	22 50	44.00

Source: Questionnaire and communication

OBSERVATION

It was observed from the table 1 that 64.70 % library users opined that goodwill generates among the users through maintaining good relations by the library staff, 64% rendering quality services, 92% leadership, promptness, and skillful policy, 84.70 by creating well behaviour with various types of readers, 47.05 % library staff should be punctual in timing with attachment and affinity in public library readers as they comes under the umbrella of grass root users, 44% readers of NGO libraries says that there should be quality collection with modernize techniques in the library.

VIEWPOINTS OF LIBRARY GOODWILL

A library's goodwill is an interesting concept with many different aspects relating to intellectual capital. The cadre wise survey of libraries was carried out to observe the various kinds of viewpoints that shape a library's goodwill and exists as an intangible resource in a library.

- Infrastructure
- Collection Development
- Financial Resources
- Human Resources
- Library Services
- Modernize Facilities for Users
- Coordination and cooperation of Library staff
- Users' satisfaction

Table 4: Intellectual capital resources

Related directly to the library	Related indirectly to the library
Programmes of advertising campaign	Information policy makers
Reputation of library	Information regulators

User relationship, loyalty, trust with library	Broadcast license
User training programme	Unemployment, economy
Information suppliers and publishers	Mass media
Information Literacy Programme	University and Research organization
Adult Education Programme	Shareholders agreement
Library and Information networks	Royalty agreements
Personality contacts and partnership	Special interest groups
Public relation	Societies
Technology sharing agreements	National Government contracts
Web enterprises, user relationship	Regulatory approvals

Figure 1: Library Perspectives of Goodwill

6.2. USER’S GOODWILL AND ITS IMPACTS ON LIBRARY

Table 5: Users goodwill and its impact

Group	Nature of Libraries	Nature of impact	Value of impact		
			Total	Valid	Value %
A	Academic Libraries	intangible asset	120	97	80.83
B	Research Libraries	valuable for development	40	35	87.50
C	Special Libraries	encourage to improve services support to increase users	40	27	67.50
D	School Libraries	full utilization of resources	100	77	77.00
E	District Libraries Public Libraries	Goodwill is the reward of services of library and staff support to increase users	140	121	86.42

F	NGO Libraries	develop automatically	publicity	40	37	92.50
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Source: Questionnaire, internet, mobile and verbal communication

OBSERVATION

It was observed from the table 1 that 80.83 % users expressed their views that goodwill is the intangible asset of library, 87.50 % shows valuable for development, 67.50 % presents to encourage and to improve library services and support to increase number of users, 77 % utilize full available resources of library. The 86.42 % users opined that Goodwill is the reward of services of library and staff and support to increase quantity of users for reading and 92.50 % suggested to develop publicity of library automatically.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was concluded that Goodwill is an intangible asset that is listed collaterally in the balance sheet of library and goodwill although intangible assets have no physical form; their presence increases the services and importance of library. The goodwill generates among the users through maintaining good relations by the library staff, rendering quality services, good leadership, promptness in services and facilities, and skillful policy, by creating well behaviour with various types of readers.

8. REFERENCES

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